

From Intent to Action: Systematic Literature Review on Research Approaches to Consumer Repurchase Behavior in E-Commerce

Muhamad Rachmat Gunawan ¹[0000-0002-6143-9231], Febriliyan Samopa ²[0000-0002-6590-1710], and Ahmad Muklason ³[0000-0001-7620-7532]

^{1,2,3} Sepuluh November Institute of Technology, Surabaya, Indonesia
rachmatg@gmail.com

Abstract

The e-commerce industry has witnessed exponential growth, particularly catalyzed by the COVID-19 pandemic, with a market valuation reaching \$4.28 trillion in 2020. This surge has prompted an influx of new business models and highlighted the critical role of efficient logistics in customer satisfaction. However, research on e-commerce has predominantly focused on consumer behavior, with a notable gap in the methodological review of repurchase intention and behavior. This systematic literature review seeks to fill this gap by analyzing primary research articles that apply established research frameworks from other disciplines to the e-commerce context. The Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) is explored as a lens to understand consumer repurchase intentions, acknowledging the challenge of the intention-behavior gap or "intention erosion" over time. The review process involved a methodological appraisal using the Watase Uake Research Collaboration Tools, with data extraction focused on study populations, contexts, theories, hypotheses, and variables. Findings are synthesized following the SWiM guidelines due to the heterogeneity of the data. This review pioneers a methodological roadmap for future e-commerce research, emphasizing strategies for bridging the intention-behavior gap and strengthening customer retention in the volatile digital market..

Keywords: e-shopping experience, customer experience, repurchase intention, repurchase behavior.

Biography:

Muhamad Rachmat Gunawan, ORCID: 0000-0002-6143-9231

Febriliyan Samopa, ORCID: 0000-0002-6590-1710

Ahmad Muklasonm ORCID: 0000-0001-7620-7532